

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369550335>

STUDENT SATISFACTION TOWARDS EDUCATIONAL SERVICES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Article · March 2023

DOI: 10.37867/TE150111

CITATIONS

0

READS

261

2 authors:

Soumya Ranjan Das

University of Hyderabad

4 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Lopamudra Gochhayat

University of Delhi

3 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

ISSN No. 0974-035X

An indexed refereed & peer-reviewed journal of higher education

Towards Excellence

UGC-HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT CENTRE
Gujarat University, Ahmedabad-380009, Gujarat, India

STUDENT SATISFACTION TOWARDS EDUCATIONAL SERVICES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Mr. Soumya Ranjan Das
Ms. Lopamudra Gochhayat

Abstract

If the number of higher education institutions is growing quantitatively, its quality needs to be aligned with it. Student satisfaction towards the educational services needs to be assessed to find out its level of educational services. Therefore, the objective of the study is to study the educational services of higher education institutions and the satisfaction of students towards it. Also, this study aims to find out the difference in students' satisfaction and educational services with reference to institutions and gender. The researcher has followed the descriptive survey method to conduct this study. 218 postgraduate students from the two universities of Odisha have participated in this study. The findings of the study revealed that, there is a significant contribution of educational services on students' satisfaction of higher education. No significant difference has been found in education service quality and students' satisfaction with reference to institution & gender.

Keywords Student Satisfaction, Educational Services, Higher Education

Introduction

In our daily lives, services and satisfaction are expected in each & every sector of society. The services provided by the institution or any other determine our satisfaction level. Like this, we can also see the education sector, such as the education services which may include the availability of infrastructural facilities for the teaching-learning process and educational outcome, also plays a vital role. We all know that India is the third-largest next to the United States & China. Lee & Anantharaman, (2013) reports that as more higher education institutions become aware that they operate in a cutthroat service sector, they adopt business attitudes. In many higher education institutions, students are seen as clients, and their pleasure becomes a key strategic goal. High-scoring institutions prioritise providing a quality education, which attracts students as attractive choices and results in high enrolment rates and low dropout rates.

In India, as per the latest report of the (University Grants Commission, 2022), the total number of higher education institutions is 1043 in 2022. Higher education prepares its leader in various sectors of society, so the higher education system of any nation can be considered the country's backbone. Therefore, the quality of the higher education system must be

emphasised to produce quality products, i.e., Student with the required contemporary knowledge and skills in order to provide market-driven academic and career programmes, excellent teaching, learning environments, enough student support services and higher education institutions must establish their fundamental aims and objectives to satisfy stakeholders of education (Ibekwe, 2006; Kaur, 2010 as cited in (Kaur, 2015).

If we focus on the AISHE (All India Survey of Higher Education), then, in Odisha there is also a substantial increase of 8.7 per cent in student enrolment in the last five years. It is also a fact that there is a decline of as 24,000 students' enrolment in 2019-20 compared to 2018-2019. In Odisha, there are 9.94 lakh higher education students enrolled overall in 2019-20, compared to 10.19 lakh in 2018-19 and 9.14 lakh in 2015-16. The Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) has increased by 1% at the national level, from 26.3% in 2018-19 to 27.1% in 2019-20. We discover that both India and Odisha experience a decline in average college enrolment. India's average college enrolment in 2019-20 is 680, down from 682 in 2018-19 (Parida, 2021).

According to the report, the state has six private universities, one state open university, three deemed-to-be universities, sixteen state universities, five institutions of national importance, three state universities, and one central university. In addition, there are 1,087 colleges, of which 67 percent are private, aided, and unaided colleges, and 33 percent are government colleges. Compared to the national average of 30, Odisha has 24 colleges per one lakh people. (Biswal, 2021).

The higher authorities of the institution should maintain awareness of students' expectations, academic preferences, and quality perceptions of the educational environment in order to make the institution progressive and effective (Palacio, Meneses, and Perez 2002) as cited in (Usman, 2010).

So, assessing the effectiveness of the educational services of higher education is very important in the 21st century. Then, we can conclude that the institution is providing educational services according to the needs and demands of the students.

Literature Review

Brown & Mazzarol (2008), in their study "The importance of institutional image to student satisfaction and loyalty within higher education", Student satisfaction, which is predicted by how the host university is perceived, is found to be a strong predictor of student loyalty. Although perceived quality of "human ware" (such as people and processes) and "hardware" (such as actual service elements and infrastructure) has an effect on perceived value, this was shown to be weak and ambiguous. According to undergraduate students at Xiamen University of China, overall service quality and its eight sub-variables (non-academic aspects, academic aspects, teaching methods, industry links, programme issues, reputation, access, cost, and student satisfaction) are all positively related to student satisfaction. Non-academic aspects and student satisfaction also have a positive and strong relationship (Huang, 2009). According to Gruber et al. (2010), a rather consistent person-environment relationship underlies students' happiness with their university. Thus, perceived quality disparities of provided services and the surrounding environment appear to be quite well reflected in

students' satisfaction. Students loved their school placements and the community they were in. The majority of students expressed dissatisfaction with the university buildings and the standard of the lecture halls. According to Wilkins & Balakshnan's (2011) study, branch campuses in the UAE generally had high levels of student satisfaction. The most important variables in determining whether or not a student at a branch campus in the UAE was satisfied with their school overall were the calibre of the lecturers, accessibility of the resources, and the efficient use of technology. In their study, "Service quality and student satisfaction: a case study on private institutions in Bangladesh," Asaduzzaman, Hossain, and Rahman (2013) examined students' satisfaction along with five elements of service quality (tangibility, responsiveness, reliability, assurance, and empathy). The findings showed a substantial link between all of the constructs and student happiness. Factor 1, which accounts for the majority of the variance (34%) and has eigenvalues larger than 3.00, is by far the most significant (10.596). According to Stukalina (2014) "student satisfaction and motivation can be modelled on a number of predictors (determinants) represented by a set of indicators associated with different aspects of the integrated educational environment." The association between student satisfaction and school reputation was fully moderated by student loyalty and school repute (Wong, Woo & Tong, 2016). Siming et al. (2015), reports that some students are motivated by a sense of accomplishment, others by assisting others, while yet others are motivated by personal fulfilment. Still other students are fulfilled by the development of their personalities, personal values, and psychological needs. According to Kaur and Bhalla (2015), academic facilities, student support services, placement services, the learning environment, extracurricular activities, knowledge upgradation, academic staff, academic facilities, and infrastructure facilities are the most crucial factors.

Razinkina et al. (2018) studied on "Student satisfaction as an element of education quality monitoring in innovative higher education institution", and the result revealed that a high level of student satisfaction with education, i.e., 66% of the surveyed students. There is interconnection between the indicators on which the parameters of the concept of student satisfaction are based. Mondal, (2018) finds that the undergraduate students belonging to government and private colleges perceive differences in service quality in relation to faculty personnel, physical infrastructure, programme reputation, administrative personnel, curriculum and access to infrastructural facilities. However, across responsiveness there is no difference in perceptions of both the groups. Another study conducted by Alhassan et al. (2018) indicates that the graduates were very satisfied with the general conduct of operations in the University and most of them were willing to further their education in the University. They were however, quite dissatisfied with the existing health services and facilities, sporting facilities and the general security situation on the various Campuses of the University. Chandramohan (2019), in his study "Student Satisfaction through Service Quality: A Review on Higher Education Sector" finds that student satisfaction has significantly been shifted from the fundamental satisfaction indicators. High student mobility and digital learning and teaching mechanism are identified as some of the important parameters for the student satisfaction in higher education institutes. Appuhamilage & Torii (2019) conducted a study on "The impact of loyalty on the student satisfaction in higher education: a structural equation modelling analysis". The findings of the study revealed that satisfaction has a

positive direct impact from services and financial support provided by the university. And also, loyalty has a positive strong impact on student satisfaction. On the contrary, satisfaction reveals a positive strong direct impact on loyalty too. Furthermore, there is an indirect impact of image, services and perceived value on loyalty. All the goodness of fit indices is at acceptable levels. Thus, the satisfaction of students seems to reflect quite well from the above construct, image, services, financial support and perceived values. According to regression relationships for loyalty model, student satisfaction has shown significant strong impact on loyalty. Munshi (2019) studied on Antecedents and Consequences of Student Satisfaction in Higher Education Context & and result shows that among the various components service quality, faculty individual attention had the highest effect on student satisfaction & the student satisfaction has a positive effect on institute image and word of mouth which subsequently has an effect on trust and commitment towards the institute. According to Amoako and Gylmah (2020), who examined "the impact of loyalty on the student satisfaction in higher education: a structural equation modelling analysis," the university's services and financial assistance have a favourable direct impact on student contentment. Additionally, loyalty has a favourable, significant effect on student satisfaction. On the other hand, satisfaction shows a large positive direct impact on loyalty as well. Additionally, loyalty is impacted indirectly by perceived value, services, and image. All goodness of fit indices are within reasonable bounds. Thus, the aforementioned construct, image, services, financial assistance, and perceived values seem to mirror the pleasure of students fairly well. According to Mulyono et al. (2020), students' satisfaction significantly mediated the relationships between academic performance and loyalty, non-academic performance and loyalty, reputation and loyalty, and campus access and loyalty; however, the relationship between programme issues and loyalty was not significantly mediated by students' satisfaction. The majority of students are happy with the amenities that the university offers. These outcomes ought to make it possible for Amity University to develop a more solid strategic plan to increase student retention and holistic success (Ranjan et al., 2020). Sneha, Sengar, and Gupta (2020)'s study, "Establishing the Relationship Between Service Quality and Student Satisfaction," indicated that all aspects of service quality like tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, and empathy had a significant impact on students' satisfaction, with the exception of assurance. In addition, the study found a significant relation between each of the variables examined. The results of a study by Venkateswarlu et al. (2020) entitled "Determinants of the Satisfaction of Students Studying in Private Universities—Application of Kano Model" showed that the world-class infrastructure and state-of-the-art technology for academic delivery were the two most important factors influencing student satisfaction at private universities. The expense of the programme, which is an important consideration to take into account, is the only element in which students have expressed a modicum of unhappiness. Dinh et al., (2021) study's from, "Vietnamese Students' Satisfaction toward Higher Education Service: The Relationship between Education Service Quality and Educational Outcomes," revealed that Hue University student satisfaction with education service was consistent with the theoretical model's five dimensions, which include access to education service, facilities and teaching equipment, educational environment, educational activities, and educational outcomes. The satisfaction with educational results is influenced

by the satisfaction with all dimensions of the quality of the education services, ranging from dimension 1 to dimension 4, with educational activities having the greatest influence.

Enhancing the quality of educational services in higher education is a concern for all parties involved in education in the 21st century, as the previous study (Amoako & Gyimah, 2020) reveals. Therefore, the customer's satisfaction, i.e., the student of higher education, must be studied to determine the level of their satisfaction towards the educational services provided by the educational institutions. In this purpose the researcher has gone through various previous related literatures and found that there are very rare studies in the area of student satisfaction and educational service quality in the Indian context and specifically in the context of Odisha. As day by day, higher education institutions are increasing; in that manner, the quality must be balanced. In Odisha, as per the AISHE report 2019-2020, the higher education institution is increasing in number. Hence, the researcher has taken this study. The present study aims to find out the satisfaction of higher education students towards the educational services provided by the higher education institutions concerning the various elements of education service quality such as tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy.

Objectives of the Study

1. To ascertain the nature of educational services of higher education institution.
2. To ascertain the nature of student satisfaction of higher education institution towards educational services.
3. To study the individual contribution of Tangibility, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance and Empathy in predicting satisfaction of higher education students.
4. To find out the difference in educational services of higher education students with reference to their institution.
5. To find out the difference in educational services of higher education students with reference to their gender.
6. To find out the difference in student satisfaction towards educational services of higher education with reference to their institution.
7. To find out the difference in student satisfaction towards educational services of higher education with reference to their gender.

Hypotheses of the Study

H₁ There is a significant individual contribution of tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy in predicting student satisfaction of higher education students.

H₀₁ There is no significant difference between institutions in educational services of higher education.

H₀₂ There is no significant difference between institutions in student satisfaction of educational services of higher education.

H₀₃ There is no significant difference between gender in educational services of higher education students.

H₀₄ There is no significant difference between gender in student satisfaction of educational services of higher education.

Methodology

This study is quantitative in method. The researcher has followed the descriptive survey design to conduct the research. This study has been carried out by taking the two institutions, i.e., Utkal University, Vanibihar, Bhubaneswar, Odisha and Ravenshaw University, Cuttack, Odisha, as the sample of the study; because the two institutions are remarkable & renowned institutions of the state. The researcher has selected these two institutions by following the purposive sampling method. After that, data were collected from 218 students of the concerned universities. The following tables show the demographic structure of the sample.

Table :1 Demographic Structure of the Sample

S.I No	Variables	Dimensions	Frequency
1	Gender	Male	84
		Female	134
2	Institution	Utkal University	113
		Ravenshaw University	105

By going through several related studies, the tool of the present study has been designed such as (Rajput, Sengar & Gupta, 2019; Hasan et al. 2008; Asaduzzaman, Hossain & Rahman 2013 & Parasuraman et al. 1985). In this tool total of 33 items relating to five dimensions such as tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy have been included to assess the educational services of higher education. Second to assess the satisfaction level of the higher education student's, the researcher has included six items relating to their satisfaction.

Before the analysis of the collected data, the researcher has tested the reliability of the instrument to assess its internal consistency of the instrument by employing the Cronbach's Alpha by SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science Research). Here, the overall Cronbach Alpha value for all the five domains is 0.932, which is a very good value and greater than 0.7 (Nunnally, 1978). The most reliable value is 0.70 but, in literature, values above 0.5 are also

considered appropriate (Hammed & Amjad, 2011). Table no 2 shows the overall Alpha value of the instrument which includes 33 items.

Table:2 Reliability Statistics of Overall item of Service Quality

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Number of Items
0.932	0.936	33

The table no 3 illustrates the Cronbach Alpha value of each dimension separately. The reliability statistics revealed that the tangibility with 12 items ($\alpha=0.827$) and the reliability with 08 items ($\alpha=0.799$) was found to be reliable as the alpha is >0.70 threshold (Hair et al., 2013). The other three dimensions, such as Responsiveness, Assurance and Empathy, have ($\alpha=0.769$), ($\alpha=0.825$), and, ($\alpha=0.561$) respectively. All the individual items have Corrected items -Total correlation > 0.300 .

Table:3. Reliability statistics of Service Quality

Dimensions	No of items	Cronbach's Alpha (α)
Tangibility	12	0.827
Reliability	08	0.799
Responsiveness	05	0.769
Assurance	06	0.825
Empathy	02	0.561

As the table 4 shows, the satisfaction tool consisting of 06 items has been tested with the Cronbach Alpha, and it has an overall $\alpha=0.930$, which is very appropriate for the reliability of internal consistency.

Table:4 Reliability Statistics of Overall item of Students Satisfaction

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.930	0.931	06

Result and Discussion

The collected data were analysed by using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social sciences). The researcher has used both descriptive and inferential statistics for the analysis of the data.

As the researcher has employed the instrument to measure the educational service and student satisfaction, descriptive statistics has been used to ascertain the nature of both the educational

services and student satisfaction. The result of the study is presented in the following tables according to the sequence of the objectives. The first objective was to ascertain the nature of educational service of higher education. Therefore, to ascertain the nature of this data researcher has presented the following frequency analysis table.

Table:5 Descriptive statistics of educational service scores in higher education institutions

N	218
Mean	129.67
Std. Error of Mean	1.208
Median	130.00
Mode	134
Std. Deviation	17.841
Skewness	-0.724
Std. Error of Skewness	0.165
Kurtosis	2.666
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.328
Minimum	38
Maximum	165
Sum	28269

The above table no 5 shows the overall mean, median, mode, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis value of the service quality score of 218 samples of students. The total mean is 129.67 median value is 130.00, mode is 134. The standard deviation of the distribution is 17.84, representing the spread of the scores from the mean. The value of skewness is -0.724, which shows the distribution is negatively is skewed. The value of kurtosis is 2.666, which is higher than the normal distribution i.e., 0.263. Therefore, the distribution of the score of service quality of higher education institution is Platykurtic.

Like the educational service, the data relating to the student satisfaction towards it has presented in the following table no 6.

Table: 6 Descriptive statistics of Student Satisfaction Score

N	218
Mean	25.10
Std. Error of Mean	0.311
Median	25.00
Mode	24
Std. Deviation	4.585
Skewness	-1.405
Std. Error of Skewness	0.165
Kurtosis	2.916
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.328
Minimum	6
Maximum	30
Sum	5471

Table no 6 depicts that the Mean of the overall satisfaction scale is 25.10, Median 25.00, and Mode 24. The standard deviation is 4.585. The value of Skewness -1.405, which means the distribution of the student satisfaction score is negatively skewed. The kurtosis of the

satisfaction score is 2.916, which is higher than the kurtosis's normal value, i.e., 0.263. As service quality score of the higher education students, the distribution of the satisfaction score is Platykurtic.

The literature says that as the educational service quality increases that also affects the level of student satisfaction (Alves & Raposo, 2010). Therefore, the first H₁ alternative hypothesis was to study the individual contribution of the five dimensions of educational services in higher education, such as tangibility which includes the physical provisions such as infrastructure etc, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy of the teaching and non-teaching staff. In order to find out the individual contribution of the five dimensions of educational services on student satisfaction, the researcher has employed multiple regression, which result is presented in the following table no 7.

Table: 7 Model Summary for the contribution of service quality towards Higher Education

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.715 ^a	0.512	0.500	3.240

a. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy, Tangibility, Responsiveness, Assurance, Reliability

From the above table it is clear that the coefficient of determination or the R² is 0.512, which means that about 51.2% of the variation in the student satisfaction of higher education is explained by the variation in the independent variables: i.e., Tangibility, Responsiveness, Reliability, Assurance & Empathy of service quality dimensions. Here, the regression equation is showing very useful for making prediction since the value of R² is 0.512.

Table: 8 ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2334.921	5	466.984	44.474
	Residual	2226.056	212	10.500	0.000 ^b
	Total	4560.977	217		

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy, Tangibility, Responsiveness, Assurance, Reliability

The above ANOVA table shows that the F value is 44.474, and p value is 0.000 < 0.05 level of significance, therefore, the overall above result shows that Service quality of higher education (Tangibility, Responsiveness, Reliability, Assurance and Empathy) has significant contribution on Student satisfaction in higher education institution. Here the p-value < 0.05, so the researcher retains the alternative hypothesis, i.e., There is a significant individual

contribution of tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy in predicting student satisfaction of higher education students is retained. The other researcher (Daud et al., 2019), (Malik, Danish & Usman, 2011) has found the same result. The result of this study is also aligned with the other studies as quality educational services influences student satisfaction (Arokiasamy and Abdullah 2012; Yadav 2012; Encabo 2011; Arambewela and Hall 2009).

Table: 9 Shows the coefficient result of the regression of various domains

		Coefficient				
Model		Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.193	1.651		0.722	0.471
	Tangibility	0.099	0.044	0.156	2.274	0.024
	Reliability	0.255	0.085	0.274	3.009	0.003
	Responsiveness	0.063	0.097	0.049	0.648	0.517
	Assurance	0.253	0.101	0.208	2.510	0.013
	Empathy	0.466	0.214	0.149	2.178	0.031

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

The above coefficient table no 9 indicates unstandardised Coefficient B value and standardised value. The regression coefficient for the predictor variables is Tangibility (0.099), Reliability (0.255), Assurance (0.253), At the 0.05 level of significance, empathy (0.466) is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). But because $p > 0.05$, responsiveness (0.063) is not significant at the 0.05 threshold of significance. Therefore, four of the five predictor variables have a significant impact on student satisfaction on higher education.

In the above standardized table, the Reliability has the largest beta coefficient i.e., 0.274, and the smallest beta coefficient is Empathy having 0.149. Therefore, one standard deviation increases in Reliability of service quality contribute an increase of 0.274 in the standard deviation of student satisfaction in higher education. Likewise, one standard deviation increase in Tangibility and Assurance of service quality will bring increase of 0.156 & 0.101 in student satisfaction.

The result is also aligned with the result of Thai Son et al. (2018), and Haddad & Badran (2018), that all the factors have significantly contributed to the student satisfaction. According to Manik et al. (2017), all factors except assurance had a positive impact on student satisfaction, including reliability, responsiveness, and empathy. In our context the, responsiveness is not influencing significantly to the satisfaction of the student. Therefore, the responsiveness needs to be emphasized at institutional level which will increase the student satisfaction in higher education.

The demographic variables such as Institution and Gender have been taken into consideration in analyzing the data for both the educational service and student satisfaction. Therefore, to test the null hypothesis, the independent sample 't' test has been employed to find out the difference between these variables, which is presented in the following table.

- Institution and Student Satisfaction in Higher education

Table: 10 Independent sample 't' test of student satisfaction score with reference to Institution

Institution	N	Mean	SD	S _{ED}	df	p-value	Level of Significance (0.05)
Ravenshaw University	105	25.65	3.908	0.619	216	0.087	Not Significant
Utkal University	113	24.58	5.033				

From the above table 10 the overall result indicates that there exists no significant difference in mean scores of the two universities i.e., Utkal & Ravenshaw University, at 0.05 as the p value is greater than the significance level. That is, the average performance score of Ravenshaw University ($M = 25.65$, $SD = 3.908$) was not significantly different from that of Utkal University ($M = 24.58$, $SD = 5.033$). Hence, the hypothesis "There is no significant difference between institutions in student satisfaction of educational services of higher education is retained.

- Gender and Student Satisfaction in Higher Education

Table: 11 Independent sample 't' test of student satisfaction with reference to Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	S _{ED}	df	p-value	Level of Significance (0.05)
Male	84	25.31	3.802	0.639	216	0.588	Not Significant
Female	134	24.69	5.022				

Table no 11 shows that the p value is higher than the 0.05 level of significance and it means that with reference to no difference exist between male and female students as the average performance of Male ($M= 25.31$, $SD = 3.802$) was not significantly different from the of female counterpart ($M= 24.69$, $SD= 5.022$). Therefore, the null hypothesis "There is no significant difference between gender in student satisfaction of educational services of higher education" is retained. The present result of the study is aligned with the previous research such as (Ilias et al. 2008, Cortes, Lounsbury, Saudargas and Tatum, 2000; Rosenthal, Folse, and Alleman, Bourdreaux, Soper and Bergen, 2000; Carey et al. 2002).

- Educational Service and Institution

Table:12 Significance of difference in the mean score of Ravenshaw and Utkal University towards different dimensions of educational services

Dimensions	Institution	N	Mean	SD	S _{ED}	P value	Level of significance (0.05)
Tangibility	RU	105	47.06	5.240	0.976	0.105	Not Significant
	Utkal	113	45.47	8.633			
Reliability	RU	105	32.10	4.068	0.669	0.656	Not Significant
	Utkal	113	31.80	5.624			
Responsiveness	RU	105	18.25	3.402	0.479	0.056	Not Significant
	Utkal	113	19.17	3.652			
Assurance	RU	105	24.93	3.154	0.511	0.776	Not Significant
	Utkal	113	24.79	4.262			
Empathy	RU	105	7.90	1.252	0.199	0.902	Not Significant
	Utkal	113	7.93	1.641			
Total Service Quality	RU	105	130.24	13.710	2.423	0.654	Not Significant
	Utkal	113	129.15	21.014			

RU- Ravenshaw University

The above independent sample 't' test clearly illustrates that in every dimension there exist no significant difference between gender with reference to educational service provided by the higher education institutions. The p value in each dimension is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Also, the overall output of the data shows that there exists no significant difference between the two institutions i.e., Utkal University and Ravenshaw University, with reference to educational service provided by them as the p (0.654) > 0.05 level of significance. It means the educational service of both institutions is statistically same.

- Educational Services and Gender

Table: 13 Significance of difference in the mean score of male and female students towards different dimensions of educational services

Dimensions	Gender	N	Mean	SD	S _{ED}	P value	Level of significance (0.05)
Tangibility	Male	84	46.71	6.234	1.007	0.439	Not Significant
	Female	134	45.93	7.796			
Reliability	Male	84	31.13	4.528	0.681	0.055	Not Significant
	Female	134	32.54	5.113			
Responsiveness	Male	84	18.10	3.532	0.491	0.038	Significant
	Female	134	19.12	3.527			
Assurance	Male	84	24.56	3.888	0.524	0.355	Not Significant
	Female	134	25.04	3.683			
Empathy	Male	84	7.82	1.433	0.204	0.444	Not Significant
	Female	134	7.98	1.484			
Total Service Quality	Male	84	128.32	15.572	2.484	0.354	Not Significant
	Female	134	130.52	19.134			

As the result of in the institution, the overall result of service quality with reference to gender shows that no significant difference exists between gender with reference service quality provided by the higher education as the $p (0.354) > 0.05$ level of significance. But suppose we focus on the dimension of Responsiveness, in that case, we will find that a slight statistically significant difference exists between gender with reference to the responsiveness of service quality provided by the institution with Male (mean = 15.10 SD= 3.532) & female (Mean =19.12, SD= 3.527). Which means males are treated with lower responsiveness than female & as result shows, female are treated with slightly more responsiveness to educational services than male.

The other researcher also found that the same result as this study showed, i.e., gender has no significant difference in educational service (joseph & joseph, 1998, Ilias et al., 2008), also this result contradicts with the result of (Soutar & Mc Neil 1996), which shows that a significant difference exists between gender in which male are more satisfied than their female counterpart.

Conclusion

From the above analysis, it is clear that overall, five dimensions such as tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance & empathy, has a significant contribution to the student satisfaction. From that, we can conclude that if the educational service quality improves then

the student satisfaction would increase. If we focus on the individual contribution of the five constructs, then it is clear that except responsiveness, all other four factors have a significant contribution on student satisfaction. The most influencing factor is the reliability which significantly influences the student satisfaction, and the lower is empathy. As we see that both the institutions are doing their academic activities & giving educational services by keeping consistency in it as the factor reliability has strong influence on the student satisfaction. And also, we can conclude that overall, the students are satisfied, and there is also no significant difference found in student satisfaction with reference to institution and gender, and also educational service has been found to be no significant difference in gender and institution, but responsiveness has some difference in gender, i.e., female have more response than boys as they are treated as per their need by the institutions.

Recommendation

We saw that from the individual contribution of service quality factor, responsiveness does not significantly influence student satisfaction. So, the institution needs to take care of that in the aspect of availability of various academic provisions and channels to address their problem & help them in complain and query. This study was limited to the two institutions of Odisha, i.e., Ravenshaw University & Utkal University, due to limited time, money and energy. Further research may need to be conducted by taking more institutions of Odisha. Other studies may be conducted by taking another aspect such as assessment, administration services etc. Case study may be conducted by taking typical institution of the Odisha also.

References

- Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A. & Berry, L. L (1996). The behavioural consequences of service quality. *Journal of Marketing*, 60(2), 31-46. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1251929>
- Soutar & Margaret. (1996). Measuring Service Quality in a Tertiary Institution. *Journal of Educational Administration*. 34(1), 72-82. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09578239610107174>
- Joseph, M. & Joseph, B. (1998). Identifying needs of potential students in tertiary education for strategy development. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 6(2), 90-96. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09684889810205741>
- Corts, D. P., Lounsbury, J. W., Saudargas, R. A., & Tatum, H. E. (2000). Assessing undergraduates' satisfaction with their major department: A method and case study. *College Student Journal*, 34(3), 399–408. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2000-16248-008>
- Alves & Aposo. (2007) Conceptual Model of Student Satisfaction in Higher Education, *Total Quality Management and Business Excellence*.18(5):571-588 <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783360601074315>
- Hasan, H. F. A., Ilias, A., Rahman, R.A. & Razak, M.Z.A. (2008). Service Quality and Student Satisfaction: A Case Study at Private Higher Education Institutions. *International Business Research*, 1(3), 163-175. Retrieved from <https://www.ccsenet.org/journal/index.php/ibr/article/view/982>
- Gruber, T. et al. (2010). Examining student satisfaction with higher education services: using a new measurement tool. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 23 (2), pp. 105 - 123. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1108/09513551011022474>
- Endris, S. (2008). Gene Conserve - Articles - Articles - - Articles - - Articles - Gene Conserve - Articles - Articles - Volume 7 - Issue 30 - October / December , 2008 . *Production*, 7(27), 2008–2010. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s>
- Kaur, H. (2015). Satisfaction of Students towards Quality in Higher Education- A Study of Higher Education Sector Punjab (India). *Pacific Business Review International*, 8(6), 83–91.
- Lee, J., & Anantharaman, S. (2013). Experience Of Control And Student Satisfaction With Higher Education Services. *American Journal of Business Education (AJBE)*, 6(2), 191–200. <https://doi.org/10.19030/ajbe.v6i2.7684>
- Usman, A. (2010). The Impact of Service Quality on Students' Satisfaction in Higher Education Institutes of Punjab. *Journal of Management Research*, 2(2), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.5296/jmr.v2i2.418>
- Wilkins, S. & Balakrishnan, M. S., (2013). Assessing student satisfaction in transnational higher education, *International Journal of Educational Management*, Vol 27(2), pp. 146-153. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/2572133/Assessing_student_satisfaction_in_transactional_higher_education

- Asaduzzaman, Hossain & Rahman (2013). Service Quality and Student Satisfaction: A Case Study on Private Universities in Bangladesh, *International Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*. Vol. 1, No. 3, 2013, pp. 128-135.
doi: 10.11648/j.ijefm.20130103.11
- Endris, S. (2008). Gene Conserve - Articles - Articles - - Articles - - Articles - Gene Conserve - Articles - Articles - Volume 7 - Issue 30 - October / December , 2008 . *Production*, 7(27), 2008–2010. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s>
- Kaur, H. (2015). Satisfaction of Students towards Quality in Higher Education- A Study of Higher Education Sector Punjab (India). *Pacific Business Review International*, 8(6), 83–91.
- Lee, J., & Anantharaman, S. (2013). Experience Of Control And Student Satisfaction With Higher Education Services. *American Journal of Business Education (AJBE)*, 6(2), 191–200. <https://doi.org/10.19030/ajbe.v6i2.7684>
- Usman, A. (2010). The Impact of Service Quality on Students’ Satisfaction in Higher Education Institutes of Punjab. *Journal of Management Research*, 2(2), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.5296/jmr.v2i2.418>
- Stukalina, Y. (2014). Identifying predictors of student satisfaction and student motivation in the framework of assuring quality in the delivery of higher education services, *Business, Management and Education* 12(1): 127–137. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3846/bme.2014.09>
- Rajput, S., Sengar, A. S., & Gupta, S. (2019). Establishing the relationship between Service Quality and Student Satisfaction. In Proceedings of 10th *International Conference on Digital strategies for Organisational Success* Retrieved from <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3320678>
- Manik et al. (2017). The impact of academic service quality on student satisfaction. MPRA Paper No. 80878, posted 19 Aug 2017 14:15 UTC Retrieved from <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/80878/>
- Al-Haddad, S., Taleb, R.A. and Badran, S. (2018). The impact of the education services quality on students’ satisfaction: an empirical study at the business schools in Jordan. *Int. J. Business Excellence*, Vol. 14, No. 3, pp.393–413. retrieved from <https://www.inderscience.com/info/inarticle.php?artid=89799>
- Thai Son et.al. (2018). Measuring Students’ satisfaction with higher education service – An experimental study at Thainguyen University. *International Journal of Business Marketing and Management*. <https://www.ijbmm.com/paper/April2018/2143693869.pdf>
- Daud, Ali, Jantan (2019). Influential Determinants of International Students’ Satisfaction in Higher Education. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*. Volume-8, Issue-2S11 DOI: 10.35940/ijrte.B1091.0982S1119

Towards Excellence: An Indexed, Refereed & Peer Reviewed Journal of Higher Education/
Mr. Soumya Ranjan Das & Ms. Lopamudra Gochhayat/ Page 141-157

Napitupulu et al. (2018). Analysis of Student Satisfaction Toward Quality of Service Facility. IOP Conf. Series: *Journal of Physics*: Conf. Series 954 (2018) 012019
doi :10.1088/1742-6596/954/1/012019

Chandramohan, S. (2019). Student Satisfaction through Service Quality: A Review on Higher Education Sector. *Archives of Business Research*, 7(7), 242-249.
DOI:<https://doi.org/10.14738/abr.77.6779>

Parida, A. (2020, June 15). AISHE-20 report: Higher education a priority of Naveen Government. *The pioneer: State Edition Bhubaneswar*.
<https://www.dailypioneer.com/2021/state-edition/aishe-report-odisha-far-behind-national-averages.html>

Biswal, B. (2021, June 19). AISHE report: Odisha far behind national averages. The pioneer: State Edition Bhubaneswar.<https://www.dailypioneer.com/2021/state-editions/aishe-report--odisha-far-behind-national-averages.html>

University Grants Commission. (2022). (Consolidated list of all Universities) Retrieved from
<https://www.ugc.ac.in/oldpdf/consolidated%20list%20of%20all%20universities.pdf>

Mr.Soumya Ranjan Das
Doctoral Research Scholar
Department of Education & Education Technology, University of
Hyderabad, Gachibowli
E.mail- soumyaranjandas670@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0668-1981>
and
Ms. Lopamudra Gochhayat
M.Phil Scholar
School of Education, Ravenshaw University, Cuttack. India
E.mail- lopamudra85988@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2864-9691>